

SIGNIFICANCE OF HONESTY FOR EFFECTIVE GOSPEL MINISTRY*

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Abstract

The paper argues for the significance of honesty as one of the parameters for effective Gospel ministry. The premise of its argument was based on the seeming abandonment of moral standards and Christian principles in favour of expediency by some Gospel ministers, which has led to apparent manifestations of demeaning atrocities among the members of the clergy. The novelty of its literature review underscores the insufficiency of research on honesty in particular, though there are discussions around it from various paradigms. The paper adopted an analytical approach. The findings of the paper revealed that honesty is critical in the area of the call, character and practice of the Gospel minister. In addition, honesty is significant in that it helps build a Christian community and enhances the Christian mission; it pleases God and makes the Gospel minister God's delight among others. The paper concluded with the affirmation that the effectiveness of any Gospel minister is dependent on the honest lifestyle of the minister. Furthermore, honesty is of utmost importance in human relations because every social activity, and every human experience where people are to act in concert, is impeded when honesty is lacking among them. Moreover, honesty as projected in the paper is not just truth-telling; it is truth-living.

Keywords: Honesty, Gospel ministry, Minister and Effective.

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Introduction

Paul in his charge to Timothy in 1 Timothy 3:1 – 10 enumerates some virtues to look out for in anyone who desires to serve in church leadership position, which one may consider as Gospel ministry today. Among these virtues is integrity which is implied severally on the list. This presupposes that honesty in complement with others virtues is critical for effectiveness in the Gospel ministry. Regrettably, some contemporary Gospel ministers seem to have “abandoned moral standards and Christian principles in favour of expediency or pragmatism. The underlying philosophy is based on accomplishing goals by whatever means necessary.”¹ Emiola Nihinlola corroborates this assertion as “The Christian gospel is being bastardized and polluted in Africa. Many people who engage in lifestyle not consistent with the gospel are, however, claiming to be born-again.”² With these assertions, it is evident that the concern of some contemporary Gospel ministers has shifted from living the Christian faith to the competition of acquiring material possessions with their colleagues. This they validated by their attitudes and the emphasis made on ministry matters.

Consequently, one wonders if the Gospel ministry can be carried out with meaningful impact without recourse to honest lifestyle in company of other virtues. Besides, does being dishonest have anything to do with the effectiveness of a minister of the Gospel? These and some other issues are the burdens of the paper. Therefore, the paper argues for the significance of honesty for an effective Gospel ministry. At first, the paper advances the imperative of honesty in light of the current dilemma in the Gospel ministry; it then discusses the essentials for effective Gospel ministry before enumerating the significance of honesty.

The Imperative of Honesty in Light of the Current Dilemma in the Gospel

Ministry Gospel

Being genuinely called to the Gospel ministry is a noble calling which demands a sober reflection on the side of anyone God graciously helps to answer such a call (1 Tim. 3:1–5). The peculiarity of that calling has prompted scholars to pen down various aspects of concern that bother on the dilemma, prospects and challenges involved since it is a leadership position. Alluding to the dilemma in the Gospel ministry, both Emiola Nihinlola and Esther Ayandokun, in separate articles, maintain that many church leaders are no longer disposed for Spirit-led decisions because of physical and material gains of the ecclesiastical offices.³ Ayandokun puts it thus: “Those who claim to belong to Christ and have received theological training have thrown away Christian virtues and sometimes display actions and behaviours that we dare not mention or see among those who have known Christ.”⁴ She affirms that the dissatisfaction about the quality of the Christian life of many ministers manifesting in their lack of competence is glaring to many observers.⁵ In the well-researched articles, Nihinlola and Ayandokun did not give sufficient attention to the subject of integrity in their discussions. For clarity, in a different paper on “The Challenges of Ministry Leadership,” Nihinlola avers personal devotion, complete obedience, self-control, good communication, and humble use of authority as some of the challenges.⁶

In another study, Peter O. Awojobi and Timothy Agboluaje, in their discussion on Samuel's leadership as model for African leaders, argue that the current generation can learn a lot from Samuel because the truth he proclaimed and the moral standards he set had much influence on the people of Israel.⁷ It is worth noting that they alluded to the honest lifestyle of Samuel. However, the virtue was not further expatiated. In the

same vein, in an anthology, *Ministry Enrichment Series Volume 8*, edited by Emiola Nihinlola and Folashade Oloyede, various scholars approach the subject of Christian Leadership from different paradigms varying from the Challenges of Ministerial Leadership, Leadership Lifestyle and Principles, Failure of Leadership, Selfishness in Leadership, Leadership and Self Discipline, and Incompetence in Leadership, among others.⁸ Whereas all the articles discussed were very relevant to the Gospel ministry, many seems not to focus on the subject of honesty, hence, the need to call attention to the subject.

Consequently, discussing the imperative of honesty becomes germane. One, honesty is an ethical virtue necessary for exercising the Christian faith. Lockyer argues, “The virtue of honesty is a moral excellence or goodness (Phil. 4:8) ... considered a necessary ingredient in the exercise of faith (2 Peter 1:3, 5).”⁹ In the same vein, Farley maintains that in the biblical sense, honesty “Involves a positive response to God, and to what God has set in motion.”¹⁰ It is an activity to which the whole conforms with its highest end, which is to glorify God and is in the teachings of Jesus.¹¹ These two descriptions affirm that honesty, apart from being a necessary ingredient in the exercise of faith, is also a positive response to God and what God has set in motion. To be honest, therefore, is to live in conformity with moral excellence to the glory of God in the exercise of faith. That is so important that it stemmed from the conviction that Christian character, moral disposition and habits are as important as any Christian statement of faith. Perhaps anything short of that may be regarded as dishonesty.

Two, honesty is pivotal in promoting harmonious interpersonal relationships. Cochran drawing her biblical positions of honesty, affirms, “The scripture upholds honesty as a quality closely related to the excellence of character – the habitual practice

of honesty is necessary for harmonious relationships.”¹² In addition, the Bible further considers honesty not only with truth-telling but also with the pursuit of justice and faithfulness in interpersonal relationships.¹³ This implies that honesty plays a vital role in cultivating harmonious relationships through the excellence of character, pursuit of justice and faithfulness in interpersonal relationships.

Three, lack of honesty is associated with evil, and God detests it (Ezek. 22:11 – 13; Acts 5:1 – 11; and 2 Cor. 4:2). “More often than not, acts of deceits are unequivocally associated with evil, impurity, and opposition to the good. The overall commitment to honesty is rooted in a belief in God's truth and goodness and the unity of truthfulness and love.”¹⁴ Invariably, lack of honesty is evil, impure and opposition to the good, which God does not tolerate from any of His children. Sequel to the above discussion of honesty, it is pertinent to query the crucial demands for effective Gospel ministry in order to ascertain the relevance of honesty to the Gospel ministry. This remains the focus of the paper in the next section.

Critical Essentials for Effective Gospel Ministry

The first essential for an effective Gospel ministry is God's call of the Gospel minister. In their discussion on laying the foundation for effective ministry, Wilson and Hoffmann maintain that who the pastor is, begins with two key issues; intimacy and calling.¹⁵ On his calling, they argue that the pastor ought to be honest in his conviction that God indeed called him/her, not other persons or things.¹⁶ This aspect of call is crucial because a dishonest minister of the Gospel in the area of being genuinely called by God can never render an effective ministry. Nihinlola asserts, “Ministry is a matter of the 'heart.' The heart of the minister must be right with God”¹⁷ in the aspect of being

called by God. It takes the sincerity of the Gospel minister to affirm that God actually called him/her to launch into the Gospel ministry and be effective. Several atrocities and moral decadence associated with some contemporary Gospel ministers put a question on the genuineness of the call of God on such people.

The second essential for effective Gospel ministry is the life and character of the person. An anonymous author notes that “effective leadership is best understood not by focusing only upon personality traits in the leader, but upon the relationship between the leader and those being led.”¹⁸ The author argues that one of the four significant factors ever-present for effective leadership is the leader's character, which generates trust on the part of followers.¹⁹ In contrast to that position, a lack of good character may be observed among some Gospel ministers who are careless about the dignity of their office and condescend to engage in the use of abusive language,²⁰ mismanagement of funds, and sometimes diversion of designated church funds, engagement in immoralities, among others.

Furthermore, the foundation and dimension of Christian character is the minister's union with Jesus Christ. The character of Christ in the pastor should produce particular moral excellences crucial to the leader's effectiveness—honesty, integrity, fairness, compassion, service to others, a life of prayer, and total dependence upon God for strength and guidance. The evidence of such character in leaders is that people trust such leaders, and such leaders trust the people they lead.²¹ Unfortunately, the congregation of some contemporary Gospel ministers cannot trust their pastors. Since they have noticed that their pastors do not stand firmly for righteousness, they manipulate the truth and stylishly avoid speaking the truth when a supposed 'reputable Christian' or even a colleague is erring spiritually.

Another essential for effective Gospel ministry is following God's pattern and doing it in God's way. When God requested the Israelites under the leadership of Moses to construct a tabernacle for Him, He (God) instructed that it must be according to His pattern. The Bible says, "...Make this tabernacle and all its furnishings exactly like the pattern I will show you." (Ex. 25:8 – 9, NIV) To show the seriousness of the point, God had to reiterate to Moses, "See that you make them according to the pattern shown you on the mountain." (Ex. 25:40, NIV). The Gospel ministry is not a vocation that one does anyhow one feels. One would hear some Gospel ministers saying things like "It is my ministry, and I have to do it my way" or something like "I am the one God called, not you and you have to follow my way" (speaking to their members). That may result when a member seems to be pointing the attention of the pastor to a specific error he is committing.

More so, one must render a Gospel ministry according to the will and methods of God, the owner of the ministry. Effectiveness in the ministry demands that the minister follows God's laid down pattern. Every Gospel minister must be like Moses, who, after completing the Tabernacle, the Bible says, "the lampstand was made exactly like the pattern the LORD had shown Moses."²² Any Gospel minister who does not do ministry according to God's pattern cannot be adjudged effective. In fact, Paul calls them enemies of the cross.

In wrapping up this section, it is pertinent to note what Jerry Akinsola believes concerning leadership effectiveness. He argues that "some Church fathers identified certain character deficiencies that would disqualify a leader from being effective ... laziness, gluttony, greediness, lust, envy, rage (anger) and pride."²³ Consequently, anyone doing ministry with any of the issues Akinsola raised would never be effective

provided he or she claims to be doing a Gospel ministry. These essentials are a few among several others. Nevertheless, does honesty have any significance for an effective Gospel ministry? This is addressed in the subsequent section of the paper.

The Significance of Honesty for Effective Gospel Ministry

This section examines the significance of honesty for effective Gospel ministry. The points that are raised hereunder reiterate the need for Gospel ministers to genuinely conduct their lives and ministries in honesty and in the fear of the Lord.

Honesty makes Christian leadership possible

Honesty is so paramount that it makes Christian leadership possible. “Christian leaders must live the truth and tell the truth because that is leadership.”²⁴ What Gehman implies here is that honesty builds confidence in the leadership and makes the community develop. Prime and Begg, concurring with Gehman, maintain that the life and character of Gospel ministers serve as an example for others in holiness and uprightness (Titus 1:8).²⁵ Humans naturally would like to follow a leader whose life is always challenging them positively.

Honesty aids the multiplication of the influence of Christian values.

According to Oladimeji, “The lifestyle of a leader is crucial to what will happen to the followers. A tree produces its like; it is imperative for the leader to be honest.”²⁶ This implies that a congregation will take after her leader's attitude. It is on this note that Gehman enumerates some reasons for the significance of moral integrity for Christian leadership, one of which is “That God commands Christian leaders to have integrity in three dimensions; holiness, veracity and faithfulness.”²⁷ In addition, Kostenberger opines that having a passion for ministry without truth-telling or right living would lead

to misleading the congregation.²⁸ Just as Prime and Begg further affirm that Gospel ministers are to be like God in holiness,

“Our lifestyle should bear the evidences of our heavenly citizenship (Philippians 3:20), in that it indicates where our treasure is. While on the one hand, we are to be marked by the willingness to work hard (2 Thess. 3:7 – 10), it is to be equally clear that the love of money is not our motivation (1 Tim. 3:3), and that we want nothing to do with dishonest gain (Titus 1:7).²⁹

Therefore, unless a Gospel minister possesses and practices honesty through moral integrity in all facets of life, his/her ministry will not affect the congregation. Honesty builds a Christian community and enhances the Christian mission. live their words, keep their promises, serve their community ... show us Jesus Christ, then Christian community is built and Christian mission is enhanced.”³⁰

However, when the opposite occurs, the contrary will be the case; “when leaders ... fail to live with integrity, the fallout is deadly serious. It poisons the community, destroys trust, torpedoed a coherent and unified mission and, most seriously of all, betrays the cause of Christ's gospel and dishonours the God whom we serve.”³¹ It is pertinent to assert that the essence of the Gospel ministry is for the edification of the body of Christ, the Church, such that each member would attract members of the society to Christ through mission endeavours. Therefore, when the virtue of honesty is evident in the life and character of a Gospel minister, doing a Christian mission would be easier.

Honesty makes the Gospel minister complete.

Honesty makes the Gospel minister complete. Ezell affirms that honesty entails being authentic, sincere, genuine, and legitimate. Being somewhat simulated, forged, faked, or false is dishonesty. Honesty communicates a desire to live in the open.³² A lack of honesty looks for cover, protection, or obfuscation. Living in the shadows, to some extent, is a lifestyle. However, honesty makes the minister complete, like the building

superintendents of Joash in 2 Kings 12:15, who were completely honest and thus were made complete in their honesty. The text (2 Kings 12:15 NIV) says of these building superintendents, "they acted in complete honesty." The value of complete, whole, and integrity all share a standard significance. Integrity comes from the word *integer*, just as it is used in numbers. An integer is a whole number.³³

Being honest pleases God and makes the Gospel minister God's delight

Honesty is also significant because it pleases God and makes the Gospel minister God's delight. A Gospel minister ought to be honest because of the social ramifications mentioned earlier. Nevertheless, more critically, one should practice honesty because it pleases God. As children of the light, ministers and Christians should conduct themselves with integrity and faithfulness. Solomon says, "Lying lips are detestable to the LORD, but faithful people are His delight" (Proverbs 12:22). Gospel ministers ought to live genuinely because they abide by a different standard and a different guide – God through the Holy Spirit. Society affirms tolerance is the norm; Christianity affirms truth is the norm. Christianity asserts that it is good and wrong and that there are absolutes, in contrast to society's assertion that there is no such thing as right or wrong.³⁴ If society reduces truth to personal preference as long as one is sincere, Christians should say truth is truth regardless of one's preference. It is because one can be sincere but sincerely wrong. Ezell also contends that we live in a world that values tolerance over truth. If people are taught to prioritize relativism over truth today, it is ideal that Christians who identify as Christ's followers—the one who referred to himself as "The Truth"—become recognized for their integrity.³⁵

Consequent to the above-listed points, it is evident that the effects of a dishonest minister of the Gospel will surely manifest as a reproach to the Gospel of Christ. Rather

than attracting believers and unbelievers to the Gospel, he would be repelling them from Christ. These are some of the ethical criteria or conditions that every Gospel minister can develop. Unless they are jealously upheld and imbibed, there can be no effectiveness in the ministry.

Conclusion

The paper has established the significance of honesty in light of current dilemma in the Gospel ministry. It has also examined the essentials for effective Gospel ministry. They are very critical if imbibed alongside other biblical virtues for any Gospel minister who truly desires effectiveness. More so, the significance of honesty in the discharge of ministry responsibilities cannot be over-emphasized. It can therefore be concluded that the effectiveness of any Gospel minister depends on the honest lifestyle of the minister, which is just one of the several other crucial virtues expected from a Christian, including a Gospel minister. Furthermore, honesty is paramount in human relations, including the Gospel ministry. Every social activity, every human experience where people are to act in concert, is impeded when people are not honest with one another. The honesty here is not just truth-telling; it is truth-living. It is the kind of honesty that God sought through the prophet Jeremiah, "Go up and down the streets of Jerusalem, look around and consider, search through her squares. If you can find but one person who deals honestly and seeks the truth, I will forgive this city" (Jer. 5:1 NIV).

Endnotes

¹ John F. MacArthur, *The Power of Integrity: Building a Life without Compromise*. (Wheaton: Crossway Books, 1997), vii.

² . Emiola Nihinlola, "Stewardship of the Gospel" *Ministry Enrichment Series Volume 6: Living and Preaching the Gospel*, Emiola Nihinlola and Folashade Oloyede, eds. (Ogbomoso: NBTS Publishing Unit, 2019), 17.

- ³ . Emiola Nihinlola, “Spiritual Leadership in West Africa” and Esther O. Ayandokun, “The Imperatives of Integrity in Leadership Challenge in Africa” both in *Leadership in Africa: Challenges for Theological Education, WAATI Papers No. 6*, Emiola Nihinlola, Thomas Oduro and Deji Ayegboyin, eds. (Ibadan: Baptist Press (Nig.) Ltd, 2012), 21 – 29 and 120 – 135 respectively.
- ⁴ Esther O. Ayandokun, “The Imperatives of Integrity in Leadership Challenge in Africa” *Leadership in Africa: Challenges for Theological Education, WAATI Papers No. 6*, Emiola Nihinlola, Thomas Oduro and Deji Ayegboyin, eds. (Ibadan: Baptist Press (Nig.) Ltd, 2012), 124.
- ⁵ Ayandokun, 124 – 133.
- ⁶ Emiola Nihinlola, “The Challenges of Ministerial Leadership” *Ministry Enrichment Series Volume 8: Principles and Practice of Christian Leadership*, Emiola Nihinlola and Folashade Oloyede, eds. (Ogbomosho: Kingdom Impact Publishing and Media Ltd. NBTS, 2021), 21 – 22.
- ⁷ Peter O Awojobi and Timothy Agboluaje, “Samuel’s Exemplary Leadership as a Model for Theological Educators in Africa” *Leadership in Africa: Challenges for Theological Education, WAATI Papers No. 6*, Emiola Nihinlola, Thomas Oduro and Deji Ayegboyin, eds. (Ibadan: Baptist Press (Nig.) Ltd, 2012), 75.
- ⁸ Emiola Nihinlola and Folashade Oloyede, eds. *Ministry Enrichment Series Volume 8: Principles and Practice of Christian Leadership*, (Ogbomosho: Kingdom Impact Publishing and Media Ltd. NBTS, 2021).
- ⁹ Herbert Lockyer, Sr. ed. *Nelson’s Illustrated Bible Dictionary*. Herbert Lockyer, Sr. ed. (Nashville: Thomas Nelson Publishers, 1986), 1088.
- ¹⁰ Benjamin W. Farley, *In Praise of Virtue: An Exploration of the Biblical Virtues in a Christian Context*. (Grand Rapids: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 1995), 9.
- ¹¹ Farley, 9.
- ¹² Elizabeth Agnew Cochran, “Honesty” *Dictionary of Scripture and Ethics*. Joel B. Green ed. (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2011), 374.
- ¹³ Cochran, 374.
- ¹⁴ Ibid, 375.
- ¹⁵ Michael Todd Wilson and Brad Hoffmann, *Preventing Ministry Failure: A Shepherd-Care Guide for Pastors, Ministers and Other Caregivers*. (Downers Grove: InterVarsity Press, 2007), 25 – 27.
- ¹⁶ Wilson and Hoffmann, 26.
- ¹⁷ Emiola Nihinlola, “The Biblical Portrait of a Gospel Minister” Emiola Nihinlola and Samuel Olugbenga Akintola, eds. *Ministry Enrichment Series Volume 4: The Dynamics of Competent Gospel Ministry*, (Ogbomosho: Kingdom Impact Publishing and Media Ltd. NBTS, 2017), 33.
- ¹⁸ *Effective Leadership in the Church*. Grand Rapids: Sustaining Pastoral Excellence, 2005, 20. (Accessed February 13, 2022).
- ¹⁹ *Effective Leadership in the Church*, 21. (Others are conviction in the leader (which helps the congregation discern its purpose and vision); Competencies in the leader (which help a congregation function as a healthy system); and Confluence of leader (congregation, time, place, ministry opportunity, and resources. See *Effective Leadership in the Church*, 22).
- ²⁰ For instance, the writer was in a church where the pastor was abusing the congregation for not giving enough instead of encouraging them.
- ²¹ *Effective Leadership in the Church*, 22.
- ²² See: Num. 8:4 NIV.
- ²³ Jerry Akinsola, “Keys for Effective Christian Leadership in the Twenty-first Century” in *Effective Christian Leadership in the Twenty-first Century*. Edited by Samson Olasupo Ayokunle. (Ibadan: Baptist Press, 2010), 9 – 10.

²⁴ Richard J. Gehman, *Learning to Lead: The Making of a Christian Leader in Africa*. (n. p.: Oasis International Ltd, 2008), 172.

²⁵ Derek Prime & Alister Begg, *On Being a Pastor: Understanding Our Calling and Work*. (n.p.: Oasis International LTD, 2004), 40.

²⁶ Samuel Oluwafemi Oladimeji, *Stewardship Handbook for Churches*. (Ibadan: Simplex Creations, 2016), 17.

²⁷ Gehman, 169 – 172.

²⁸ Andreas J. Kostenberger, *Excellence: The Character of God and the Pursuit of Scholarly Virtue*. (Wheaton: Crossway, 2011), 124.

²⁹ Prime and Begg, 41.

³⁰ Jonathan Lamb, *Integrity: Leading with God Watching*. (Nottingham: Inter-Varsity Press, 2006), 20.

³¹ Lamb, 20.

³² Rick Ezell, "Honesty: The Complete Virtue." 2014

www.lifeway.com/en/articles/sermon-honesty-the-complete-virtue (Accessed February 27, 2022).

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ Ibid.